

The Regiospecific Catalytic Inversion of (+)-Dehydroabietic Acid to (-)-Podocarpic Acid

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New work is described on a novel two-step sequence involving the regiospecific Friedel-Crafts Acetylation and palladium-catalysed inversion of a steroidal-type A/B ring juncture to an antipodal A/B ring juncture.

SEVERAL years ago, we reported a simple two-step sequence involving the catalytic transformation of the natural steroidal-type ring juncture to an antipodal A/B ring juncture¹. This paper reports the details of work on the catalytic transformation of the diterpene A/B ring juncture to the antipodal system, specifically the regiospecific synthesis of methyl (-)-podocarpate (V) from methyl (+)-dehydroabietate (I) in an overall yield of 65%.

Recently, Tahara and Akita² have reported on the treatment of methyl (+)-dehydroabietate (I) and methyl 5 α , 10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (II) with anhydrous aluminium chloride under Friedel-Crafts conditions. We have shown that compound II is obtained in a yield of 75% by treatment of methyl 5 α , 10 β -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(VI) with anhydrous aluminium chloride.

However, attempts to alter the 10-methyl orientation of methyl (+)-podocarpate(VII), methyl (+)-callitrisate (VIII), and several other 16-oate derivatives under Friedel-Crafts conditions were unsuccessful. These 16-oate compounds were converted to deisopropyl derivatives (e.g. XVI) or structurally unidentified 9,10-secotype compounds.

From the results of the studies on the 15- and 16-oate compounds using several Bronsted and Lewis acids as the catalyst, it seems reasonable to conclude that the isomerization reaction proceeds through a comparatively stable benzenium ion and according to the Felkin principle, the energy barrier will be minimal through the transition state.³

Accordingly, it is suggested that the formation of the π -complex between aluminium chloride (Lewis acid) and the aromatic ring system is an important factor in the reaction of the 15-oate series as well as the 16-oates one. It is believed that the reaction proceeds by an

ionic dealkylation mechanism which is kinetically controlled. However, in the 16-oate series, if cleavage of the bond between C-9 and C-10 occurs, the carbonium ion cannot achieve complete sp^2 hybridization because of the electronic interaction between the C-4 axial carbomethoxy group and the C-10 methyl group. On the other hand, in the 15-oate series, the C-10 carbonium ion transition state can achieve complete planar sp^2 character because of the 1,3-diaxial methyl interaction.³ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

As described earlier,¹ the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of III with acetyl chloride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in carbon disulfide resulted in the formation of methyl 12-acetyl-5 β ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (IV) in a yield of 43%.^{3,4} The reaction also furnished methyl 13-acetyl-5 β ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (IX) as a minor product (15% yield) and ca. 40% of the starting material (III) was recovered.⁵

Refluxing compound II with acetyl chloride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in carbon disulfide for three and a half hours gave selectively methyl 12-acetyl-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (X) as a glassy material in a yield of 75%; $[\alpha]_D +2.1^\circ$, ($c=0.22\%$ C₂H₅OH); m.p. 145-147°, as the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (Fig. 4). Furthermore, treatment of compound II with acetyl chloride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry benzene under reflux conditions for one hour afforded X in a yield of 95%, accompanied with a small amount of acetophenone. Methyl 13-acetyl-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate could not be isolated although traces were detected by gas chromatography⁵.

Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of compound X with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in chloroform gave methyl 12-acetoxy-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (XI). Without purification, the product was hydrolyzed to methyl 12-hydroxy-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (XII), m.p. 183-184°, $[\alpha]_D -6.6^\circ$ ($c=0.12\%$,

C₂H₅OH), in a yield of 62% based on the starting material (I).

When treated with palladium-charcoal catalyst in refluxing triglyme, compound X afforded IV, m.p. 158-160°, $[\alpha]_D -153.5^\circ$ in an almost quantitative yield. Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of compound IV with H₂O₂-SeO₂, followed by hydrolysis gave methyl (-)-podocarpate(V) in good yield.

Furthermore, we have examined the prolonged reaction of compound II over palladium catalyst. The products were methyl 5 α ,10 α - or 5 β ,10 α -podocarpa-6,8,11,13-tetraen-15-oate [(XIII) or (XIV)], and methyl 10 α -podocarpa-5,8,11,13-tetraen-15-oate (XV), etc.⁶ Accordingly, it is suggested that the palladium reaction proceeds via dehydrogenated intermediates over the heterogeneous catalyst.

Recently, Nasipuri⁷ has reported on the polyphosphoric acid (PPA) catalysed transformation of the diterpenoid series of racemic 5 β ,10 β -podocarpa-8,11,13-trienes to the 5 α ,10 β -type of compounds. He has

compared his results with those obtained from the palladium-catalysed isomerization reaction. Increasing interest is being shown in the difference of the mechanism involved with each catalyst.

We have synthesized methyl (-)-podocarpate(V)⁸ from methyl (+)-dehydroabietate(I) in an overall yield of a 65%. Methyl (-) podocarpate(V) may prove to be an important intermediate in the total synthesis of antipodal and/or *ent*-diterpenoids such as the bicyclic (labdanes) or tetracyclic (atisanes) terpenes.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained in KBr or Nujol mull on a JASCO IR-G instrument. NMR spectra were measured at 60 MHz using deuteriochloroform as the solvent, the chemical shifts are given in ppm using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard on a JEOL C-60 HL Spectrometer. The optical rotations were obtained in chloroform or ethanol (approximately 0.5%) on a Perkin-Elmer polarimeter 241.

Friedel-Crafts acetylation of methyl 5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (II). To a solution of the title compound (4.0 g.) in acetyl chloride (2 ml) and CS₂ (100 ml) powdered anhydrous AlCl₃ (3.9 g) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 3.5 hr. After cooling, the solvent was evaporated to dryness, and the residue was taken up to 5% HCl in chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water and then dried over anh. Na₂SO₄. After filtration, the chloroform solution was evaporated to dryness and the orange-coloured residue was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene gave methyl 12-acetyl-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(X) as a colorless glass, [α]_D+2.1° (c=0.22, EtOH), C₂₀H₂₈O₃, M⁺ 314.412, m.p. 145-147° (as 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone); yield 3.4 gr. (73.6%). IR: (nujol); 1720 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃), 1680 cm⁻¹ (COCH₃). NMR: δ 3.65 (3H, s. COOCH₃), 2.54 (3H, s. COCH₃), 1.25 (3H, s. C(4)-CH₃), 1.07 ppm (3H, s. C(10)-CH₃). (Found: C, 76.36; H, 8.38%. C₂₀H₂₈O₃ requires: C, 76.40; H, 8.34%). In this experiment, no methyl 13-acetyl-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate could be isolated although traces were detected by gas chromatography.

Palladium-charcoal catalysed inversion of methyl 12-acetyl-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate (X). To a solution of the title compound (0.5 g) in of triglyme (10 ml) was added 10% Pd-C(0.5 g). The mixture was stirred under reflux for 1 hr. After cooling below 100°, the palladium catalyst was collected and the precipitate was washed with small amounts of hot triglyme. The filtrate was poured into a mixture of crushed ice and water, then crystallized gradually. The precipitate was collected, and washed with water. Recrystallization from ethanol gave methyl 12-acetyl-5 β ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(IV) as colorless needles, (483 mg), m.p. 158-160°, [α]_D-153.5° (c=0.55%, abs. EtOH). IR: (KBr); 1681 cm⁻¹ (COCH₃), 1708 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃). NMR: δ 3.72 (3H, s. COOCH₃), 2.59 (3H, s. COCH₃), 1.31 (3H, s. C(4)-CH₃), 1.08 ppm (3H, s. C(10)-CH₃).

Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of methyl 12-acetyl-5 β ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(IV) with selenium dioxide-hydrogen peroxide.

A mixture of compound IV (325 mg.), *t*-BuOH (15 ml.), H₂O₂ (30%, 1.5 ml.) and SeO₂ (25 mg.) was refluxed for 6 hr. Ethyl acetate was then added, and the mixture washed with water, then with a dilute solution of FeCl₂ in HCl and again with water. The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anh. MgSO₄. The resulting solution was evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in *N*-methanolic KOH solution (15 ml.) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. After cooling, the mixture was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, then dissolved in chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed with diluted HCl, water, and then dried over anh. MgSO₄. After evaporation of the organic layer, the remaining crystalline material was chromatographed over a silica gel column. Elution with benzene gave 213 mg. of starting material; subsequent elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (3:1) yielded 23 mg. (27% based on recovered starting material) of methyl

(-)-podocarpate(V), m.p. 211-212°; [α]_D-102.8° (c=0.53, EtOH). Use of 70% H₂O₂ in this reaction afforded V in a yield of 68.5%. With 90% H₂O₂ the yield of V was 89.5%.

*Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of methyl 12-acetyl-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(X) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid* A mixture of compound X (1 g.), *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (1 g) and chloroform (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was washed with a 5% aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution and then water. The chloroform layer was dried over anh. MgSO₄ and evaporated to dryness. The residue consisted of 1.219 g. of crude methyl 12-acetoxy-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(XI). Without purification, the crude material (XI) (1.219 g.) was dissolved in *N*-methanolic KOH solution (50 ml.) and the mixture was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, then dissolved in chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed with dilute HCl, water, and then dried over anh. MgSO₄. After evaporation of the organic layer, the crystalline residue was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) gave 551 mg. (61.8% based on starting material) of methyl 12-hydroxy-5 α ,10 α -podocarpa-8,11,13-trien-15-oate(XII), m.p. 183-184°, [α]_D-6.6° (0.12%, EtOH), IR: (nujol); 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH), 1725 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃). NMR: δ 3.62 (3H, s. COOCH₃), 1.17 (3H, s. C(4) CH₃), 1.07 ppm (3H, s. C(10)-CH₃). C₁₈H₂₄O₃, M⁺ 288.374. (Found: C, 74.69; H, 8.43%. C₁₈H₂₄O₃ requires: C, 74.97; H, 8.39%.)

Treatment of methyl (+)-callitrisate(VIII) with anhydrous aluminium chloride. To a solution of methyl (+)-callitrisate(VIII), (265 mg.) in anh. benzene (100 ml.) was added finely pulverized anh. AlCl₃ (300 mg). The mixture was stirred for one hr., maintaining the temperature of the solution at 30-33°. After decomposition with dilute HCl, the benzene layer was washed with 5% aqueous KOH and then with water, and dried over anh. MgSO₄. Evaporation of benzene gave a residue which was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene-chloroform (9:1), gave crystalline methyl (+)-desoxypodocarpate(XVI). Recrystallization from methanol-water gave needles, m.p. 139-141°; yield: 183 mg. (based on methyl callitrisate), C₁₈H₂₄O₂; M⁺ 262.392.

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